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D8.3 – Publishing of New Bible and Qur'anic Commentaries Metadata on RESILIENCE (PLATFORM)

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Document Overview

The Ministero dell'Università e della Ricerca (MUR) has concluded a Grant Agreement (GA) with the ITSERR consortium (Italian Strengthening of the ESFRI RI RESILIENCE)¹ for the provision of IT services to support the existing national infrastructure and bring it to a higher level of maturity, in terms of involvement of technology and ability to increase the innovation, quality, and variety of the knowledge produced by the community of Religious Studies.

Within the structure of the ITSERR project, the Work Package 8 (WP8)–*uBIQUity*, whose title incorporates the “BI” of the Bible(s) and the “QU” of the Qur’ān, investigates the sacred texts of Christianity and Islam across diverse environments and historical periods, using both traditional and computational methods. This analysis is carried out through two extensive *corpora*: Greek and Latin Christian commentaries—broadly understood as written forms of exegesis—on the Bible(s), composed from the patristic era to the late Byzantine period; and classical commentaries on the Qur’ān written in Arabic (*tafāsīr*), dating from the rise of Islam to the 15th century. It is widely acknowledged that no text emerges in isolation, and that every text is inevitably shaped by the written (and oral) culture of its author(s). This is particularly evident in the case of ancient commentaries. Indeed, these exegetical works are intrinsically intertextual: they were composed specifically to explain and interpret, step by step, the sacred texts, and constitute a literary genre—whether Greek and Latin biblical commentaries or *tafāsīr*—that develops cumulatively, drawing on and juxtaposing different sources in relation to a given verse or passage. In this sense, the intertextual references embedded in ancient commentaries form their (in)visible framework—or, we might even say, their backbone. Whether employed consciously or unconsciously, they function as “places of memory,” making the sacred texts “ubiquitous”—hence the title of the project.

By integrating research methods from the humanities with state-of-the-art computer science, *uBIQUity* is developing a novel research tool capable of identifying biblical references, Qur’ānic quotations, and reuses of canonical and non-canonical collections of the Sayings of the Prophet (*‘aḥādīth*) in ancient and medieval Christian and Islamic works with a higher degree of accuracy than existing resources².

¹ ITSERR is a consortium composed of National Research Council (CNR), University of Modena and Reggio Emilia (UNIMORE), University of Naples L’Orientale (UNIOR), University of Palermo (UNIPA), and University of Torino (UNITO).

² For an in-depth scholarly overview and methodological reflection on intertextuality in relation to the Bible(s), along with a critical discussion of the digital tools currently available for detecting textual similarities, see A. Mambelli and M. Costa, *Exploring the uBIQUity of Biblical Texts: Tradition and Innovation in the Ancient and Digital Worlds*, in A. Melloni and F. Cadeddu (eds.), *The Digital Turn in Religious Studies. Research, Services, Infrastructures*, Göttingen: Vandenhoeck & Ruprecht, 2025, pp. 149-176; D. Dainese, L. Bigoni, and M. Zanella, *Resilient Septuagint Between Borges and Asimov: A State-of-the-Art Case of uBIQUity*, in Melloni and Cadeddu (eds.), *The Digital Turn*, pp. 177-206; D. Dainese and A. Mambelli, *Intertestualità tra Bibbie e antichi commentari cristiani: l’esempio di simul nel De Genesi ad litteram di Agostino*, in “Lexicon Philosophicum: International Journal for the History of Texts and Ideas”, 11 (2023–2024), pp. 39-65: <https://lexicon.cnr.it/ojs/index.php/LP/article/view/872/726>.

The WP8 team members are:

- Sara **ABRAM**, University of Palermo (UNIPA): Arabic texts.
- Marcello **COSTA**, UNIPA: visual communication design.
- Fabrizio **D’AVENIA**, WP8 Leader, UNIPA.
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- Anna **MAMBELLI**, WP8 Scientific Coordinator and Product Owner, University of Modena and Reggio Emilia (UNIMORE): Greek and Latin texts.
- Chiara **PALILLO**, UNIPA: visual communication design.
- Fabio **TUTRONE**, UNIPA: Latin texts.

Regarding research in the field of computer science, for the Latin section, the collaboration with the UNIMORE team composed of Davide **CAFFAGNI**, Federico **COCCHI**, Marcella **CORNIA**, Rita **CUCCHIARA**, and also with Cesare **CONCORDIA** and Carlo **MEGHINI** of the National Research Council (CNR, Pisa) is fundamental. As for the Arabic section of WP8, Giovanni **PUCCETTI** of the CNR is working on the IT side.

Concerning research and work on Ancient Greek, WP8 has decided to collaborate with the team of another project with similar aims, which has been incubated in the framework of RESILIENCE RI, namely the PRIN (Italian Research Project of National Interest, n. 20229E83B3) *Resilient Septuagint. An Initial Exploration of the Semantics of Killing and Healing in the Septuagint and its Reception in Patristic and Late Antique Sources (3rd cent. BCE-5th cent. CE)*. This PRIN project involves the *Alma Mater Studiorum* University of Bologna (UNIBO, PI Research Unit), the University of Bari (UNIBA), and the University of Catania (UNICT). The *Resilient Septuagint* team members are: Luca **ARCARI** (University of Naples Federico II), Laura **BIGONI** (UNIBO), Laura **CARNEVALE** (UNIBA Research Unit Chief), Davide **DAINESE** (Principal Investigator [PI], UNIBO), Isabella **PIGNOCCO** (UNICT-UNIBO), Arianna **ROTONDO** (UNICT Research Unit Chief and deputy PI), Giorgia **SAMPÒ** (DDC University of Southern Denmark-UNIBO), Gianluca **SCATIGNO** (UNIBO), and Marco **ZANELLA** (University of Padua-UNIBO). This collaboration between WP8 and *Resilient Septuagint* has included and will continue to include the development of a shared methodological framework and interoperable datasets for the study of Greek biblical texts and their heritage.

This document is the fifth deliverable from the WP8 of ITSERR (D8.3) and reports on the publication and use of texts, data, and metadata concerning the Bible(s), the Qur’ān, and their respective traditions of commentaries within the RESILIENCE infrastructure. Building on the outcomes of D8.1.1 (*Corpus Preparation and Algorithms*), D8.1.2 (*Whitepaper on uBIQUnity*), and the technical documentation prepared for D8.2 (*Training Material, Manual and Documentation for RESILIENCE*), this document presents **the release of the uBIQUnity platform**, initially conceived as the integration of two dedicated portals—one for Biblical

commentaries and the other for Qur’ānic commentaries—hosted on a shared infrastructure. However, for the sake of greater efficiency and functionality, **the final outcome is a unified platform that currently supports three languages (Ancient Greek, Latin, and Arabic)** and is designed to accommodate future expansions, such as the addition of Hebrew. **This platform marks a decisive step in providing Religious Studies scholars with FAIR-compliant resources that interconnect sacred texts, exegetical commentaries, and digital tools.**

1. Objectives

The main objectives of the present document are:

- To describe the publication and dissemination of data and metadata on the Biblical and Qur’anic traditions through the *uBIQUity* platform;
- To demonstrate interoperability between *corpora* and metadata prepared according to D8.1.1;
- To validate the functionality of the software developed in D8.1.2 (and partially in D8.1.3) and documented in D8.2;
- To provide the scholarly community with two prototype portals, hosted by a shared platform, which sets a new standard for tools dedicated to Religious Studies and, potentially, also for other domains.

All in all, the present deliverable will make clear that, with its careful integration of philological methods, computer science, computational linguistics, and design, the *uBIQUity* platform is a multi-faceted tool providing Digital Humanities (DH) researchers with cutting-edge facilities based on Large Language Models (LLMs), text reuse algorithms, and innovative approaches to intertextual analysis.

2. Scope

D8.3 focuses on the integration of textual *corpora* and commentary metadata into two fully functioning web portals. The scope is dual: on the one hand, *uBIQUity* consolidates and operationalizes standards for metadata preparation (as defined in D8.1.1), software infrastructure (D8.1.2), and integration (D8.2). On the other hand, it provides scholars with innovative tools to explore intertextuality, exegetical traditions, and the broader cultural contexts of Christianity and Islam. These portals serve as prototypes that show the considerable potential of *uBIQUity* as a Digital Humanities tool not only for the field of Religious Studies, but also for the wider domains of ancient and medieval intertextuality, cultural history, and literary reception.

3. State of the Art

As described in D8.1.1, existing digital tools for biblical and Qur’anic/Prophetic research suffer from fragmentation, limited accessibility, and inadequate integration of critical apparatus and

commentarial traditions. Biblical platforms usually provide only single-edition views and lack comprehensive interconnection with the *corpora* of exegetical works. In the field of Islamic scriptural studies, the state of the art is even more limited. Despite the availability of large digitized *corpora*, lexicons, and basic morphological tools, there are currently no integrated platforms specifically designed to identify and analyze text reuse and intertextuality within Islamic religious literature. In particular, the relationship between *tafsīr* and *ḥadīth* collections remains difficult to investigate computationally, due to the absence of tools supporting automatic lemmatization of inflected forms, semantic analysis, concordances, the detection of both literal correspondences and, above all, non-literal intertextual relations. Existing resources are highly fragmented and rarely interoperable, which significantly restricts large-scale, systematic analysis of exegetical and Prophetic traditions. This gap highlights the need for unified, user-friendly digital environments capable of integrating linguistic support with advanced intertextual search and visualization functionalities.

As for the Greek and Latin biblical heritage, D8.1.2 highlighted that, in general, no unified platform yet combines philological, exegetical, and computational perspectives in a way that respects both data granularity and interpretive complexity. *uBIQUity* has been designed precisely to address these gaps. In fact, while the existing platforms tend to privilege single authoritative editions without devoting sufficient attention to the diversity and complexity of textual traditions, the *uBIQUity* platform has been conceived as a node-based infrastructure enabling modularity, scalability, and adaptability to heterogeneous *corpora*.

uBIQUity overcomes the limitations of existing tools by providing an interoperable environment that enables data to be shared, connected, and extended across *corpora* and traditions. Unlike current solutions, which remain fragmented and siloed, *uBIQUity* has been designed to bridge sources and disciplines, ensuring that outputs are compatible, reusable, and sustainable for future research.

From a design perspective, its main objective is to provide a bi-dimensional workflow space that overcomes the limitations of current text-based UIs and facilitates the discovery of correlations between data that would be difficult to identify in a linear process. The existing tools, such as *Thesaurus Linguae Graecae* (TLG), *Accordance*, and *Logos* for Greek studies, *Corpus Corporum*, *Tesserae*, and *Bibindex* for Latin studies, generate friction for several reasons: their datasets are built on limited *corpora*, they are not user-friendly or fully accessible, and they do not communicate with each other because they return non-interoperable outputs that hinder data sharing.

From an IT and design perspective, *uBIQUity* introduces a significant innovation gap compared to existing digital tools used in Biblical, Qur'anic, and broader intertextual research. While current platforms generally rely on linear search interfaces, limited interoperability, and rigid data structures, *uBIQUity* adopts a computational and visual strategy specifically tailored to the complexity of philological and exegetical workflows.

On the IT side, the platform integrates heterogeneous *corpora*—Greek, Latin, and Arabic—through shared, TEI-compliant metadata structures and ingestion pipelines defined in D8.1.1 and D8.2. This ensures consistent handling of textual units, variants, and commentary metadata across traditions. The search engines developed for each language exemplify this approach: language-agnostic syntactic matching, transformer-based semantic embeddings (e.g., SPhilBERTa and Latin BERT/LaBERTa), and fine-grained text chunking for Arabic sources collectively enable multi-layer retrieval that goes beyond simple string matching. Such architectures provide rich, scalable, and FAIR-compliant data processing, which current commercial or domain-specific tools do not offer.

From a design perspective, as indicated in D8.1.2, *uBIQUity* introduced a methodological shift from traditional, list-based query interfaces to a node-based research environment. This interface models scholarly reasoning as an expandable workflow, visually representing queries, comparisons, and analytical steps as interconnected nodes. The system adapts to different cognitive styles identified during user research (survey, interviews, VARK-based assessment), offering visual, textual, and exploratory modalities within the same environment. Existing tools—such as TLG, *Logos*, *Accordance*—typically present results linearly and cannot represent the branching logic of intertextual analysis or the iterative nature of scholarly interpretation.

Furthermore, *uBIQUity* incorporates advanced visualization techniques (variant graphs, TRAViz-based alignment views, contextual maps) to support both distant and close reading. These visual metaphors reduce the friction traditionally experienced when working with multiple editions, commentaries, or apparatuses, and they enable scholars to discover correlations that remain hidden in conventional, text-based UIs.

Altogether, the combination of interoperable data models, AI-assisted retrieval, and cognitively informed design strategies defines *uBIQUity* as a next-generation platform. It not only unifies previously siloed resources but also provides researchers with a flexible, exploratory, truly interdisciplinary environment that has no parallel in current digital scholarship on religious texts.

4. Methodology

The methodology underlying the *uBIQUity* software and portals combines three foundational components:

1. Data and Metadata preparation (D8.1.1): Texts and commentaries were digitized or selected from existing digital *corpora* and structured and semantically enriched according to standardized schemas, with consistent attention to the specific requirements of multilingual *corpora* (Greek, Latin, Arabic).

2. Software infrastructure (D8.1.2): The *uBIQUity* platform provided algorithms, UI/UX design, and workflows for ingestion, search, and visualization of data and metadata.
3. Technical integration (D8.2): Detailed procedures for APIs, storage, and interoperability ensured smooth publication into the RESILIENCE environment.

All steps were designed to be aligned with FAIR principles, ensuring Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability of data. In order to reach this goal, TEI-compliant structures were used for both Biblical texts and commentaries, and the platform employed UX/UI strategies relying on graph visualizations and user-driven workflows.

While XML encoding (TEI, OSIS, EpiDoc) provides a robust hierarchical structure for textual data, the goal of interoperability across projects requires moving toward Semantic Web technologies. For this reason, the project design also considers the progressive transformation of selected resources into Linked Open Data (LOD). Using RDF (Resource Description Framework), information can be expressed as machine-readable triples (subject–predicate–object), enabling entities such as authors, works, biblical passages, and textual witnesses to be linked to external authority files (e.g., VIAF or Wikidata).

This transition is already underway for the Latin corpus, and in particular for the Latin Biblical texts. This activity, carried out by CNR-ISTI, has produced an RDF representation of the linguistic layer of the Latin Bible aligned with the LiLa (*Linking Latin*: <https://lila-erc.eu>) knowledge base. Through this integration, textual tokens are connected to lexical entries, lemmas, and morphological information provided by LiLa, establishing a first level of semantic interoperability between *uBIQUity*'s textual resources and external linguistic infrastructures. This RDF representation of the Latin Bibles therefore constitutes one of the project's existing semantic search layers and a concrete step toward a broader Linked Open Data ecosystem.

This approach allows project data to move beyond isolated XML datasets and become part of a broader semantic ecosystem, enabling cross-corpus integration and advanced queries across distributed resources. In this perspective, XML ensures internal structural consistency, while RDF and Linked Open Data support interoperability, semantic enrichment, and long-term reusability of the project's scholarly data in accordance with the FAIR principles.

4.1 Dataset Construction and Metadata-Driven Design

In *uBIQUity*, datasets were not conceived as mere digitized texts, but as structured research objects resulting from a clear methodological distinction between data and metadata. This distinction underlies all phases of corpus construction, ingestion, and publication within the platform and determines the types of scholarly queries, filters, and visualizations that *uBIQUity* can support.

4.1.1 Data and Metadata: A Foundational Distinction

Within *uBIQUity*, data consist of the textual materials themselves: biblical texts, patristic and late antique works in Greek and Latin, and Islamicate texts in Arabic (Qur'an, *ḥadīth*, *sīrah*, *tafsīr*). These texts are encoded in machine-readable formats (XML-TEI, OSIS, TEI-EpiDoc, or rule-based structured plain text formats, depending on the corpus) and represent the primary linguistic content subjected to intertextual analysis.

While this plurality of encoding formats reflects the heterogeneous scholarly traditions and existing digital editions on which the project relies, a long-term objective of *uBIQUity* is the progressive harmonization of these resources into a shared data representation model. This convergence would facilitate cross-corpus querying, simplify data integration workflows, and strengthen interoperability between textual collections originating from different linguistic and editorial contexts.

Metadata, by contrast, describe, contextualize, and connect these textual data. They include information about authorship, work attribution, textual version, editorial source, chronology, geographical context, and typology of intertextual relations. Metadata are not ancillary: they constitute the enabling layer that allows texts to be filtered, searched, mapped, and compared across *corpora* and traditions. In *uBIQUity*, data and metadata are therefore managed as distinct but interdependent components of the project's data architecture.

4.1.2 Greek and Latin Datasets: Editorial Traditions and Copyright Constraints

For the Greek and Latin *corpora*, dataset construction started from modern critical editions of biblical and patristic texts. These editions reflect complex editorial traditions and, in many cases, are subject to strict copyright restrictions. As a consequence, *uBIQUity* does not aim to replicate or redistribute full critical editions. Instead, the project adopted a selective and compliant strategy: textual data were prepared in forms suitable for computational analysis, while respecting legal constraints on reproduction and distribution.

In practical terms, this meant privileging the encoding of textual segments, identifiers, and references, rather than the wholesale reproduction of copyrighted apparatus. Where available, apparatus information was modeled at the metadata level (e.g. presence of variants, witnesses, or versional alignments), without violating licensing restrictions. Copyright considerations thus directly influenced both the granularity of the data and the design of the metadata schema, shaping what could be published openly and how editorial information could be represented indirectly.

Greek and Latin texts were encoded using established scholarly standards (TEI, OSIS, TEI-EpiDoc), ensuring consistency in the representation of textual units (books, chapters, verses, sections) and in the attribution of authors, works, and versions. This encoding supports interoperability with external authority files (e.g. VIAF, Wikidata) and enables fine-grained metadata-based filtering by author, period, region, biblical book, commentary, or textual tradition.

4.1.3 The Arabic Dataset: Heterogeneous Sources and Metadata Normalization

The Arabic component of *uBIQUity* required a different methodological approach, as detailed below (cf. 4.4). Rather than relying on newly digitized critical editions, the Arabic dataset builds primarily on the *Open Islamicate Texts Initiative* (OpenITI), which provides a large corpus of texts already available in machine-readable form. Here, the main challenge was not digitization, but harmonization.

Arabic data were ingested as structured textual content (typically in TXT format), while particular emphasis was placed on metadata normalization and enrichment. Metadata inherited from legacy repositories were often inconsistent, incomplete, or too technical for direct scholarly use. The *uBIQUity* workflow therefore included a systematic refinement of metadata fields: author names (Arabic and transliteration), chronological information (Hijrī and Gregorian dates), bibliographical references to modern editions, and geographical data were standardized and reordered according to a coherent internal schema.

This metadata architecture allows Arabic texts to function as fully contextualized research objects, methodologically comparable—though not identically—to their Greek and Latin counterparts. It also reflects the specific structure of Islamicate textual traditions, where chains of transmission, exegetical layering, and genre distinctions play a crucial role.

4.1.4 Metadata as an Operational Layer: Filters, Search, and Maps

Across all linguistic domains, metadata play a central operational role in *uBIQUity*. They are the basis for advanced filtering and search functionalities, allowing users to restrict queries by language, corpus, author, period, region, textual version, or type of intertextual relationship. Metadata also power *uBIQUity*'s visualization tools: chronological distributions, network graphs, and interactive maps rely directly on encoded temporal and geographical information.

In this sense, metadata act as a bridge between philological expertise and computational processing. They translate scholarly knowledge—about editions, traditions, and contexts—into structured information that can be queried, combined, and visualized at scale. The distinction between data and metadata thus corresponds to a functional division between textual content and research affordances.

4.1.5 Dataset-Driven Training of Latin Embedding Models

Beyond their role as publishable and interoperable research objects, the Latin datasets prepared within *uBIQUity* also contributed to the training and refinement of language-specific retrieval models. In particular, the Latin biblical *corpora* structured on a verse-level were used as a data basis for fine-tuning a sentence embedding model aimed at supporting semantic retrieval and intertextual analysis in low-resource settings.

From a data perspective, Latin biblical traditions provide a particularly suitable environment for this task. Different versions of the “same” text (e.g., Jerome’s *Vulgate* and the *Vetus Latina*) preserve a shared semantic structure while exhibiting systematic lexical and syntactic variation. This variability reflects patterns of textual transformation that are relevant for intertextual analysis, including rephrasing, paraphrase, and non-literal semantic correspondence between passages.

To exploit this characteristic, the project adopted a variant-based data augmentation strategy specifically tailored to Latin biblical material, relying on Artificial Intelligence and, in particular, on a Large Language Model (LLM) as a generative component. Starting from curated verse-level passages from the *Vulgate* (treated as a large, structurally stable source corpus), the workflow uses GPT-4 to generate additional synthetic training examples grounded in biblical language and phrasing.

Concretely, for each source passage, the LLM is prompted to produce two controlled variants: (i) a positive passage, i.e. a reformulation that preserves the meaning of the biblical verse while changing its wording and structure; and (ii) a negative passage, designed to remain lexically plausible and stylistically compatible with the domain, but to diverge semantically from the source. The latter functions as a hard negative, i.e. an example that may look similar but should not be retrieved as a true correspondence. In order to increase variability while remaining within the constraints of verse-like textual units, the prompt also asks the model to generate variants that are shorter, longer, or comparable in length to the source passage. For downstream processing and validation, GPT-4 is instructed to return the generated output in a structured JSON format (Fig. 1), ensuring consistent formatting and facilitating integration into the training workflow.

You are given a passage from an ancient Latin Bible. Your mission is to generate a positive and a negative passage for a text retrieval task in JSON format. The JSON object must contain the following keys:

- "**positive_passage**": a string, a positive passage that is different from the source passage but has the same meaning. It should be *longer than* the source passage.
- "**negative_passage**": a string, a negative passage that only appears related to the source passage. It should be *of the same length as* the source passage.

Both the positive and negative passages must be in Latin. Your output must always be a JSON object only, do not explain yourself or output anything else. Be creative!
Source passage: *In principio creavit Deus caelum et terram*

```
{ "positive_passage": "In principio omnium Deus creavit caelum  
et terram et omnia quae in eis sunt";  
  "negative_passage": "In tempore antiquo homo exploravit  
caelum et mare" }
```


Fig. 1. Prompt template employed to generate positive (meaning-preserving) and negative (lexically plausible but semantically divergent) variants for Latin biblical passages (adapted from the method described in the project's related research output).

Alongside LLM-generated variants, the dataset construction also leveraged attested correspondences between different Latin biblical versions when available. Where a *Vetus Latina* verse could be aligned with its *Vulgate* counterpart, this cross-version correspondence provided an additional positive training signal. During fine-tuning, positive examples were therefore drawn from two complementary sources: synthetic positives generated by GPT-4 and cross-version verse correspondences grounded in the underlying *corpora*. This combination increases the diversity of semantically equivalent realizations seen during training, while keeping the process anchored to *uBIQUity*'s curated textual data. Examples of synthetic positive and negative variants are shown in Fig. 2.

Overall, this augmentation strategy expands the training material in a way that directly reflects the needs of biblical intertextual retrieval in Latin. By systematically combining meaning-preserving reformulations with carefully designed hard negatives, the training process is explicitly oriented towards distinguishing genuine semantic correspondences from superficial lexical similarity.

1 John. 1.2

W_VULG *et vita manifestata est et vidimus et testamur et adnuntiamus vobis vitam aeternam quae erat apud Patrem et apparuit nobis*

and the life was manifested, and we have seen it, and testify, and declare to you the eternal life, which was with the Father, and was manifested to us

S_VL + et ipsa vita *manifestata est, et vidimus, et testes sumus, et annuntiamus vobis vitam aeternam, quae erat apud Patrem, et manifestata est in nobis*

and the life itself was manifested, and we have seen it, and are witnesses, and declare to you the eternal life, which was with the Father, and was manifested in us

Synth + et vita revelata est et conspeximus et confirmamus et annuntiamus vobis vitam perpetuam quae fuit apud Patrem et ostensa est nobis

and the life was revealed, and we have seen it, and confirm it, and declare to you the eternal life, which was with the Father, and was shown to us

Synth - et veritas declarata est et audivimus et loquimur et praedicamus vobis sapientiam antiquam quae manebat apud Patrem et cognita est nobis

and the truth has been made manifest, and we have heard it, and we speak it, and we proclaim to you the ancient wisdom which remained with the Father and was made known to us

Bar. 3.29

W_VULG *Quis ascendit in caelum, et accepit eam, et eduxit eam de nubibus?*

Who ascended into heaven, and took her, and brought her forth from the clouds?

Synth + quis in caelum ascendit, accepit et deduxit eam

Who ascended into heaven, took her and brought her down?

● longer than SRC ● of the same length as SRC ● shorter than SRC

S_VL + quis ascendit in caelum et accepit eam et deduxit eam de nubibus

Who ascended into heaven and took her and brought her down from the clouds?

Synth - quis iter facit ad caelum, contemplatur eam ex nubibus et manet in sublime, non tangit aut deducit illam in terram

Who makes a journey to heaven, contemplates it from the clouds and remains on high, does not touch it or bring it down to earth?

Fig. 2 Examples of synthetic textual variants generated by GPT-4 starting from a Latin biblical source passage (*Vulgate*). For each source verse, the model produces a meaning-preserving positive variant and a lexically plausible but semantically divergent negative variant, following explicit prompting constraints. The generation process also allows control over the relative length of the variants. During training, positive examples are drawn either from these synthetic variants or, when available, from the corresponding verse in an alternative Latin biblical version (*Vetus Latina*).

4.1.6 Methodological Implications

The construction of *uBIQUity* datasets shows that methodological choices in data modeling are never neutral. Decisions about what to encode, at what level of detail, and under which legal and technical constraints directly affect the analytical possibilities offered by the platform. By clearly separating data from metadata, by differentiating workflows for Greek/Latin and Arabic corpora, and by foregrounding copyright constraints as a design factor, *uBIQUity* establishes a transparent and reproducible methodology for the creation of FAIR-compliant datasets in Religious Studies.

This approach ensures that *uBIQUity* is not merely a repository of texts, but a research infrastructure in which data and metadata are jointly designed to support complex, multilingual, and legally compliant intertextual analysis.

Remaining within the framework of the methodology adopted by WP8, the main workflow stages of the present project and their connections to each deliverable are outlined below:

Workflow Stage	Related Deliverable(s)	Description
Digitization & Metadata preparation	D8.1.1	Guidelines for the digitization of religious texts and for structuring metadata (XML-TEI / XML-OSIS).
Software development	D8.1.2	Algorithms, UX/UI, and graph-based data exploration via <i>uBIQUity</i> .
Software development & Experience of testers	D8.1.3	<i>uBIQUity</i> dataset, functionalities, and interface assessed by potential users for critical feedback.
Technical documentation	D8.2	APIs, pipelines, and system integration into RESILIENCE.
Metadata ingestion & Portal	D8.3	Actual publication of metadata on two portals hosted by <i>uBIQUity</i> .

4.2. Metadata-Driven Workflows in *uBIQUity*

On the basis of this data and metadata architecture, *uBIQUity* operationalizes scholarly analysis through metadata-driven workflows, in which structured descriptions of texts, authors, versions, chronology, and geography are directly translated into coherent, reproducible research paths. In fact, the design of *uBIQUity* is based on the assumption that coherent and performant scholarly workflows can only emerge from a metadata-driven architecture. In the platform, workflows are not hard-coded sequences of actions, but dynamically generated research paths that arise from the structured interaction between data, metadata, and user input.

At the core of this approach lies the consistent use of metadata as an operational layer. Search initiation, filtering, comparison, visualization, and the construction of reusable research flows are all governed by metadata fields rather than by isolated textual strings. This ensures that workflows remain reproducible, transparent, and adaptable across languages and *corpora*.

4.2.1 Search Initiation and Language-Specific Workflows

Each workflow begins with the explicit selection of a reference language (Greek, Latin, or Arabic). This choice determines not only the underlying corpus, but also the metadata schema,

filters, and retrieval models that will be activated. In other words, language selection acts as a methodological switch, aligning the user's research workflow with the specific structure of the selected dataset.

Search queries are interpreted through language-specific pipelines, always mediated by metadata. For example, the same comparison criteria (exact match, inflectional match, root-based match, synonymic or structural similarity) are applied across languages, although relying on different linguistic resources and metadata fields.

4.2.2 Metadata-Based Filtering and Contextual Refinement

Once a search is initiated, metadata-driven filters allow users to refine and contextualize results. These filters do not simply restrict output but actively shape the analytical workflow by narrowing the interpretive horizon according to explicit scholarly criteria.

For Greek and Latin datasets, filters rely on metadata related to:

- textual domains (Scriptures vs. Ancient Authors)
- biblical versions and books
- authors and works
- chronology
- geographical context
- presence or absence of critical apparatus.

For the Arabic dataset, filtering is based on metadata describing:

- textual genres (Qur'an, *ḥadīṭ*, *sīrah*, *tafsīr*)
- authors and works
- chronological ranges (*Hijrī* and Gregorian)
- geographical information used for spatial visualization.

In all cases, maps, timelines, and sliders are not visual add-ons, but direct interfaces to structured metadata fields.

4.2.3 From Results to Comparison and Visualization

Search results are not treated as static outputs. Metadata associated with each result enable multiple comparison and visualization modes, such as parallel views, variant graphs, distant reading grids, and alignment-based representations. These modes are activated conditionally,

depending on the availability and type of metadata (e.g. apparatus information, structural segmentation, or similarity scores).

Sorting mechanisms—by similarity, author, or chronology—are likewise metadata-driven, ensuring consistency between quantitative ranking and scholarly contextualization.

4.2.4 Node-Based Workflows and Research Traceability

A distinctive feature of *uBIQUity* is the node-based workflow model, in which each action performed by the user (search, filter, comparison, visualization) generates a new node within a dynamic research graph. This graph is not merely a visualization, but a formal representation of the underlying metadata-driven workflow.

Users can branch their analysis by launching new searches from existing results or nodes, thereby creating alternative research paths that remain explicitly documented. Metadata ensure that each node preserves information about:

- the searched text
- applied filters
- comparison criteria
- corpus and language context.

This design guarantees the traceability and reproducibility of complex research processes, which are often difficult to document in traditional linear workflows.

4.2.5 Annotation, Evaluation, and Workflow Persistence

Logged-in users can enrich their workflows through annotations, bibliographical references, and evaluative feedback. Notes can be attached to texts, nodes, or entire workflows, while bibliographical metadata allow seamless linking to external resources (e.g. Zotero).

Completed workflows can be saved, versioned, reloaded, and exported in structured formats (e.g. JSON). In this way, *uBIQUity* workflows become reusable research objects, preserving not only results but also the methodological path that led to them.

4.2.6 Methodological Implications

By grounding workflows in metadata rather than in *ad hoc* interface logic, *uBIQUity* ensures coherence between data modeling and scholarly practice. Metadata-driven workflows align user interaction with the underlying structure of the datasets, enabling scalable, interpretable,

and FAIR-compliant research processes. This approach transforms the platform from a search tool into an environment for methodologically controlled digital scholarship.

4.3. Data Management, Retrieval Models, and UI Methodology

These metadata-driven workflows are implemented through dedicated ingestion pipelines, language-specific retrieval models, and a node-based UI/UX design, which together ensure that methodological coherence is preserved across data processing, search, visualization, and user interaction. In consistent application of these methodological principles, the implementation of *uBIQUity* occurred in three main phases:

- Phase 1: Platform configuration and deployment of *uBIQUity* as a shared hosting environment.
- Phase 2: Ingestion of data and metadata following D8.1.1 guidelines, with automated quality checks and validation.
- Phase 3: Platform development and integration with the RESILIENCE infrastructure. Notably, the *uBIQUity* platform was designed according to the node-based UI principles outlined in D8.1.2, allowing researchers to visualize intertextual connections in non-linear, associative workflows.

From what has been outlined so far it should be clear that the methodological framework underlying *uBIQUity* extends beyond the preparation of textual data and metadata: it defines a coherent technical and design strategy for how such data are ingested, processed, visualized, and explored by scholars. Building on the foundations laid in D8.1.1 and D8.1.2, the platform implements a series of methodological choices that address both computational requirements and user-centered research practices.

From a data-management perspective, the ingestion workflows adopt standardized, TEI-compliant structures for Greek and Latin *corpora*, ensuring uniformity in the representation of textual units, variants, and commentary metadata. The ingestion pipelines—developed in alignment with the specifications of D8.2—perform automated validation, versioning, and structural normalization, allowing heterogeneous sources to be indexed and queried through a shared architecture. This interoperability is strengthened by the integration of semantic models and language-specific search engines: for instance, Greek embeddings based on SPhilBERTa, contrastively trained Latin embeddings, and fine-grained Arabic chunking (500-character segments with overlap) all provide robust multi-layer search capabilities. These models ensure that syntactic, semantic, and contextual correspondences are captured systematically, supporting a unified methodology for intertextual retrieval across languages.

On the visualization and UI/UX side, *uBIQUity* adopts a methodology explicitly shaped by the user research described in D8.1.1, including interviews, surveys, and cognitive-style

assessments based on the VARK framework. These studies highlighted the need for interfaces capable of accommodating visual, textual, analytical, and exploratory approaches simultaneously. As a result, *uBIQUity* deploys a node-based interface in which each operation—query, filter, comparison, annotation, visualization—becomes a modular and traceable step within an evolving analytical workflow. This design reflects the branching logic typical of philological research: scholars frequently refine or multiply interpretive paths, compare parallel hypotheses, and return to previous states of analysis.

Visualization strategies were selected to support this dynamic research model. Tools such as variant graphs, parallel comparison views, interactive maps, or TRAViz alignments are integrated through APIs and invoked contextually within the workflow. These representations enable seamless transitions between distant reading (global distribution of intertextual links) and close reading (line-by-line comparison of variants or commentaries). The methodology also includes a structured system for annotations, allowing scholars to attach comments or bibliographical notes at any point—either to a single node or to an entire workflow—thus preserving the interpretive dimension of research within the digital environment.

In this way, the methodological choices of *uBIQUity* articulate a cohesive ecosystem: FAIR-compliant data structures, scalable retrieval algorithms, and cognitively informed visual strategies converge to support a research experience that mirrors the complexity of scholarly inquiry while surpassing the limitations of traditional, linear digital tools.

4.4. The Arabic Dataset as a Methodological Case Study

Compared to the Greek and Latin side of *uBIQUity*, the Arabic component has some distinctive features, which deserve specific attention. The Arabic component consists of a large and heterogeneous corpus, designed as a substantial case study for the investigation of intertextuality in Islamic literature. It brings together a selection of texts drawn from the main religious textual genres of the Islamic tradition (Qur'an, *ḥadīṭ*, *sīrah*, and *tafsīr*), thus enabling the investigation of how sacred and Prophetic knowledge was transmitted, reused, and reinterpreted across different literary forms.

The dataset includes the Qur'an as the foundational text of Islam, followed by an extensive selection of *ḥadīṭ* collections. These are not restricted to the six canonical Sunni compilations but also encompass non-canonical collections and collections compiled after the canonization, *Shī'ī corpora*, and works regarded as less authoritative in later scholarly traditions. In total, approximately seventy *ḥadīṭ* collections have been integrated, ensuring a broad and representative coverage of the Prophetic transmission landscape. The corpus further includes four *sīrah* works, which preserve narrative and historiographical materials frequently echoed in exegetical writings, as well as nearly one hundred Qur'anic commentaries (*tafsīr*), dating from the 8th to the 15th century.

From a data perspective, the Arabic dataset builds primarily on the *Open Islamicate Texts Initiative* (OpenITI), which aggregates texts from major online repositories and provides them in machine-readable formats. Within WP8, the Arabic materials were curated through a process of selection, verification, and harmonization of existing digital texts, rather than through new digitization efforts. The source files (typically in plain TXT format) often already contain basic internal structural markers, such as verse numbering or internal divisions of *ḥadīth* collections and commentaries.

A key focus of the work concerned metadata refinement. During early testing phases, metadata inherited from OpenITI and other legacy models were perceived as inconsistent, incomplete, or overly technical. In response, the Arabic dataset underwent substantial metadata normalization, including the addition of missing information, the harmonization of field names and field order, and a general improvement in the clarity of the information.

Each text is now accompanied by a structured metadata block combining biographical information on the author and bibliographical information on the individual work considered. Biographical metadata include the author's name (in Arabic and transliteration), dates of birth and death in both *Hijrī* and Gregorian calendars, and places of activity, supplemented by geographical coordinates used to populate a digital map. Bibliographical metadata document the work title (Arabic and transliteration), details of the modern edition (editor, publisher, place and date of publication, number of volumes), and stable references to the source repositories.

This metadata architecture ensures that Arabic texts within *uBIQUity* are not treated as isolated textual sequences, but as contextualized scholarly objects situated in time, space, and intellectual tradition. As such, the Arabic dataset provides a robust infrastructural backbone for advanced filtering, mapping, and intertextual analysis across centuries of Islamic exegetical and Prophetic literature.

5. Results

The main result of the above-mentioned undertakings is the concrete implementation and public release of the *uBIQUity* platform as an operational research environment within the RESILIENCE infrastructure. At this stage, *uBIQUity* is no longer a conceptual or experimental framework, but a fully functional system that integrates curated datasets, structured metadata, retrieval models, and user-facing workflows into a unified scholarly tool.

An extremely relevant outcome is the successful publication and interoperability of heterogeneous *corpora*—Greek, Latin, and Arabic—within a shared infrastructure. Despite the profound differences in editorial traditions, textual transmission, and legal constraints,

uBIQUnity shows that these *corpora* can be made mutually explorable through a coherent metadata architecture. Greek and Latin biblical and patristic materials, partially subject to copyright restrictions, are published in legally compliant forms that preserve their analytical value and are semantically enriched, while Arabic Islamicate texts benefit from extensive metadata normalization and enrichment. This confirms the feasibility of a multilingual and multi-traditional platform grounded in FAIR principles. Already at this initial stage, the *uBIQUnity* platform integrates datasets comprising several million tokens across the three linguistic domains, distributed over hundreds of distinct textual units (books, chapters, sections, or works), and enriched with thousands of structured metadata records describing authorship, chronology, geography, textual typology, and intertextual relations. While the scale of the *corpora* varies across Greek, Latin, and Arabic traditions, the platform shows the ability to handle heterogeneous data volumes within a unified metadata-driven framework.

A second major result concerns the operationalization of metadata-driven research workflows. As described in Section 4, metadata in *uBIQUnity* do not merely describe texts but actively govern search, filtering, comparison, visualization, and workflow persistence. In practice, this results in a research environment where scholarly reasoning is translated into reproducible and traceable digital processes. Filters based on authorship, chronology, geography, textual genre, or version are directly reflected in interactive maps, timelines, similarity rankings, and node-based research graphs. This represents a substantial advance over traditional linear search tools, which typically obscure or flatten the interpretive logic behind results.

From a computational perspective, *uBIQUnity* delivers robust, language-specific retrieval models integrated into a common methodological framework. Transformer-based embeddings for Greek and Latin, fine-tuned Latin models trained on curated and augmented biblical datasets, and chunk-based Arabic retrieval pipelines together enable multi-layer intertextual search that combines syntactic, semantic, and contextual similarity. These models are not isolated technical achievements but are fully embedded in the platform's possible workflows and visualizations, making advanced computational methods accessible and meaningful to non-technical users.

Another significant result lies in the node-based UI/UX environment, which translates complex scholarly practices into an intuitive and flexible interface. Queries, filters, comparisons, and visualizations are represented as nodes within an expandable research graph, allowing users to branch, refine, and revisit analytical paths. This design supports both exploratory and hypothesis-driven research and ensures that complex analytical processes remain transparent and documentable. The possibility to annotate, save, version, and export workflows further transforms analytical sessions into reusable research objects. In practical terms, typical research sessions generate multi-step workflows composed of dozens of interconnected nodes, reflecting successive searches, filters, comparisons, and visualizations, and confirming the platform's capacity to support complex, non-linear scholarly inquiry.

Finally, *uBIQUnity* achieves a strategic result at the level of research infrastructure. By integrating data preparation standards (D8.1.1), software architecture and design principles

(D8.1.2), and technical workflows (D8.2) into a publicly accessible research environment, the platform validates the entire WP8 pipeline and functions simultaneously as a scholarly tool, a proof of concept for metadata-driven Digital Humanities research, and a reusable model for future developments within and beyond Religious Studies. The platform has already been employed in internal testing, training activities, and exploratory research scenarios within WP8, providing iterative feedback that informed refinements in data modeling, workflows, and interface design (D8.1.2 and D8.2).

6. Conclusions

The *uBIQUity* platform represents the culmination of the methodological, technical, and scholarly work carried out within WP8, showing how texts, editions, data, metadata, computational models, and interface design can be integrated into a coherent and sustainable digital research infrastructure. The platform embodies the transition from guidelines and prototypes developed in D8.1.1, D8.1.2, and D8.2 to a tangible, operational environment that is now available to the scholarly community through RESILIENCE.

One of the central conclusions of this deliverable is that methodological clarity in data and metadata modeling is a prerequisite for meaningful digital scholarship. The explicit distinction between data and metadata, the differentiation of workflows for Greek/Latin and Arabic *corpora*, and the conscious incorporation of copyright constraints into dataset design have proven essential for building a platform that is both legally compliant and analytically powerful. *uBIQUity* shows that respecting philological complexity and legal boundaries does not limit digital analysis but instead shapes more transparent and sustainable research practices.

The project also confirms the value of metadata-driven workflows as a unifying paradigm. By grounding search, comparison, visualization, and workflow persistence in structured metadata, *uBIQUity* aligns computational processes with scholarly reasoning. This alignment enhances reproducibility, traceability, and interpretability—key requirements for FAIR-compliant research infrastructures. In this sense, *uBIQUity* moves beyond the notion of a digital “tool” and functions instead as an environment for methodologically controlled inquiry.

From a broader perspective, the outcomes of WP8 reinforce RESILIENCE’s role as a pioneering infrastructure for Religious Studies in the digital age. The platform enables comparative, diachronic, and cross-traditional analyses that challenge reductive or ahistorical readings of sacred texts, highlighting instead the richness, plurality, and intertextual depth of biblical and Qur’anic traditions. At the same time, the modular and scalable design of *uBIQUity* makes it applicable well beyond its initial domain, offering a transferable model for the study of intertextuality in ancient, medieval, and early modern cultures.

Looking ahead, the work presented in the present deliverable opens several perspectives for future development. The inclusion of additional languages (such as Hebrew), the expansion of

corpora, and the refinement of retrieval models and visualizations would further enhance the platform’s analytical scope. As *uBIQUity* enters regular use by scholars, it will also generate empirical feedback that can inform iterative improvements and new research questions. Ultimately, the platform contributes not only to the study of specific textual traditions, but also to a broader reflection on how human-digital infrastructures can support the reconstruction of cultural memory, intellectual networks, and interpretive communities across time.

7. Publications

Publications authored by some members of the WP8 team and related to this specific deliverable (D8.3) are listed below:

- S. Abram, *Shooting Stars against the Ğinn: Use and Reuse of a Ḥadīṭ in the Exegesis of Q 46:29*, in A. Melloni and F. Cadeddu (eds.), *The Digital Turn in Religious Studies. Research, Services, Infrastructures*, Göttingen: Vandenhoeck & Ruprecht, 2025, pp. 207-222.
- M. Costa, C. Palillo, and C. Ferrara, *Dal pattern alla struttura. La visualizzazione interpretativa dei dati nelle Digital Humanities*, in A. Morone (ed.), *Design Plurale. Casi e modelli alternativi per l’innovazione / Plural Design. Cases and Alternative Models for Innovation. Atti conferenza nazionale SID Società Italiana di Design (Napoli 26-27 Giugno 2025)*, Napoli: Federico II University Press, 2025, pp. 566-579.
- A. Mambelli, L. Bigoni, D. Dainese, F. Tutrone, D. Caffagni, F. Cocchi, M. Zanella, M. Cornia, and R. Cucchiara, *The Biblical Heritage in Ancient Latin Christian Literature: Advancing Intertextual Mapping Through Sentence Embeddings*, in “Umanistica Digitale”, 22 (2026), pp. 157-186. Open access: <https://umanisticadigitale.unibo.it/article/view/22160>
- L. Bigoni, D. Dainese, A. Mambelli, A. Rotondo, and M. Zanella, *The Paradigm of Killing and Healing Put to the Test of Technology: Two Case Studies in Biblical-Patristic Intertextuality*, in “Annali di Storia dell’Esegesi”, 43, 1 (2026), forthcoming. ISSN: 1120-4001
- A. Mambelli, *The uBIQUity and Resilience of Scriptures and Their Heritage*, in L. Arcari, L. Carnevale, D. Dainese, and A. Rotondo (eds.), *Pathways of Texts: From Ancient Traditions to New Computational Frontiers* [provisional title], Bologna: Marietti1820, 2026, forthcoming.
- F. Tutrone, *Dalla terra al cielo? La ‘civitas Dei’ di Agostino tra eredità classica e visione escatologica*, in “Vichiana”, 63, 1 (2026), pp. 33-49, forthcoming.

